

FOSTERING CREATIVE WORK ENGAGEMENT: THE ROLES OF KNOWLEDGE-ORIENTED LEADERSHIP AND KNOWLEDGE SHARING

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Abstract

Leadership is one of the essential elements that fosters creative work engagements in organisations. This study investigates the relationship between knowledge-oriented leadership and creative work engagement, as well as the contextual role of knowledge sharing in facilitating this relationship in Asaba, Delta State. The study used a structured questionnaire to collect data from 191 clinical workers, conveniently sampled from a state-owned hospital. The data collected was analysed using the partial least squares [PLS] structural equation modelling method. The analysis revealed that knowledge-oriented leadership has a significant and positive influence on creative work engagement, with knowledge sharing acting as a partial mediating factor. The study concluded that knowledge-oriented leaders can promote knowledge sharing to maximise their significant and positive influence on employees' engagement in creative activities. The study made several recommendations to strengthen the connections and boost employees' engagement in creative work. Among them is the need to curate leadership trainings to develop the ambidextrous behaviours associated with knowledge-oriented leadership, with a focus on enhanced communication and motivation. Furthermore, organisations should frequently develop in-house leadership trainings and sponsor employees, partly or fully, to externally organised training programmes.

Keywords: Creative engagements, employee creativity, knowledge leaders, knowledge sharing, leadership, public service organization

1. Introduction

The changing business landscape presents the ultimate challenge for managers as they grapple to find the right leadership style to enhance the engagement of employees in creative activities across organisational levels. Employees' engagement in creative work makes an important contribution to organisational development. Indeed, it plays a crucial role in fostering creative and innovative behaviours, which are crucial for thriving in environments marked by increased uncertainty and complexity. Creative work engagement can be defined as employees' participation or involvement in the creative processes associated with work. Studies have unpacked the contextual factors that enhance employees' creative work engagement and identified leadership as one of its major antecedents (Men & Jia, 2024; Nguyen & Nguyen, 2022; Saeed et al., 2019). Research has extensively discussed the role of leadership in fostering creative work engagement, but what appears new are the leadership attributes or behaviours that enhance such engagements (Sahibzada et al., 2021). The study examines knowledge-

oriented leadership [KOL], a contemporary leadership behaviour that aligns knowledge exploration and exploitation activities in response to changing work demands through their transformational and transactional qualities (Ononye & Maduemezia, 2019), with managerial priorities accorded more to enhanced motivation and communication (Donate & Sánchez de Pablo, 2014). Knowledge leaders provide a setting for the optimal flow and utility of important knowledge to foster the creative tension among employees in the workplace (Donate et al., 2022). The dynamic environment poses novel challenges and circumstances that require a leader who understands the catalytic power of knowledge and the ambidextrous nature of knowledge work to create the right context for employees to creatively perform their work roles and assignments.

This leadership style fosters desirable employee-relevant outcomes by enhancing knowledge-sharing practices (Donate & Sánchez de Pablo, 2014). Knowledge sharing is the exchange of context-specific information relevant to the execution and completion of a specified task or assignment. The mediation argument is that KOL carefully attends to the need to facilitate knowledge sharing practices to enhance employees' participation in creative work. The leadership challenge is to improve knowledge sharing and reduce knowledge hiding because of the negating effect the latter has on employee creativity (Nauman et al., 2024). According to the social exchange theory, when leaders of an organisation show supportive behaviours when building relationships with employees, they create the psychological conditions for employees to engage in the reciprocal exchange of knowledge, which influences other voluntary work attitudes and behaviours in return, such as being involved in creative work (Shamim et al., 2017). Engaging in knowledge sharing enhances employees' understanding of a problem or challenge and moves them closer to determining potential solutions. There may be a link between leadership and creative work engagement, but this study seeks to identify the specific behaviours that promote this work attitude. In this context, no single study has operationalised or examined KOL, indicating a distinct research area. Previous studies (Naqshbandi & Jasimuddin, 2018; Sahibzada et al., 2021) suggest that knowledge management practices, including knowledge sharing, could provide an intervening context in the relationship between leadership and other organisational variables. However, the mediating role of knowledge management practices on individual-level variables is still a developing area of research. Hence, there is a need to investigate how this leadership style fosters such a valued attitudinal outcome in organisations.

The study focuses on a public hospital in Asaba, Delta State, where employees' creative and innovative processes play a crucial role in providing context-specific solutions that satisfy the unique health needs of customers. Numerous studies have emphasised the relevance of creativity, particularly in light of the complex and wicked societal challenges these organisations face in a resource-constrained environment (Nguyen & Nguyen, 2022; Ononye, 2022; Thanh et al., 2022). Generally, hospitals need to discover new ideas to accelerate their responsiveness and better manage different health situations. This shows creativity and innovation are important in this public organisation setting (Akıncı et al., 2022). The coronavirus pandemic reinforced this

argument, presenting both opportunities and challenges for these organisations to be creative, particularly in managing such a novel and unprecedented health crisis. The responsiveness of public service calls for the continuous sharing, creation, and application of new knowledge in decision-making to improve the effectiveness and efficiency of its delivery. However, the bureaucratic foundations of public service organisations also pose a challenge, given that they impede the efficiency and effectiveness of knowledge-sharing activities. In this organisational setting, it may be difficult to fully exploit knowledge-sharing opportunities for value extraction (Ononye, 2021).

An organisation's ability to deliver through employees is truly dependent on the leadership style applied in practice. KOL is relevant because they seek to leverage knowledge resources through knowledge-related processes to improve the achievement of valued outcomes. The creativity process is knowledge-driven, and this leadership style may prove effective in directing and motivating the generation of context-specific solutions to evolving health problems. Ali and Sagsan (2022) observed that public managers have attempted to coordinate knowledge management activities within the bureaucratic structure of public service organisations but have yet to achieve any success. The problem partly lies with the leadership style in use, and KOL may play a decisive role in encouraging knowledge management activities in this organisation. They also found that KOL mitigates the negative impact of public bureaucracy on knowledge management coordination. Successful uptake of knowledge management allows them to access its accruable benefits and outcomes, including enhanced employee creativity, employee engagement, employee innovation, organisational learning, etc.

Given the above, the study adds to the body of knowledge by examining the influences of KOL on employees' creative work engagement, a topic not previously examined in the context of a public service organisation. The study will also confirm the argument from previous research that KOL can influence other valued constructs via knowledge management practices, of which knowledge sharing is one (Naqshbandi & Jasimuddin, 2018). Furthermore, although leadership and organisational studies have improved their focus on KOL's influences, research has not adequately discussed its roles in fostering individual and organisational-level outcomes (Rehman & Iqbal, 2020). The study responds to this call for more research on the influence of KOL on employee and organisationally relevant constructs. The study anticipates that the findings will enable targeted leadership interventions for leadership development, as well as inform strategy and practice to increase employee engagement in creative work processes.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Knowledge-oriented Leadership

Knowledge-oriented leadership (KOL) is the combination of transformational and transactional leadership behavioural qualities to stimulate the sharing, creation, and use of important knowledge in a way that brings about a collective shift in thinking and achievable outcomes (Donate & Sánchez de Pablo, 2014; Naqshbandi & Jasimuddin,

2018). The essence of combining both leadership qualities is to create an interactive and motivating context in which to coordinate employees in areas particularly sensitive to knowledge creation, knowledge integration, and learning (González-Mohino et al., 2024). KOL's ambidextrous nature makes them able to successfully adapt and manage the dynamic nature of knowledge-driven activities as the knowledge requirements change over time. According to the dynamic capability perspective, KOL's flexibility is significant in dynamic contexts because it facilitates the use of both conventional and new knowledge to create an effective response to the changing and complex demands of the innovation process. Regarding KOL's information stimulation behaviours, promoting the use of existing knowledge improves the operational efficiency of current practices through standardisation, and promoting the use of new knowledge creates new capabilities to drive new processes for strategic excellence. KOL can foster employee ambidexterity through improved communication and motivation, which has implications for employee creativity (Alghamdi, 2018).

Knowledge-oriented leadership combines the strengths of two complementary leaders' behaviours: transformational and transactional, leading to the effective exploitation and exploration of knowledge for the attainment of goals. Transformational behaviour fosters an open and inclusive environment that motivates employees to explore beyond their existing knowledge framework, seeking novel and beneficial insights in varied work situations. Support for learning, experimentation, and risk-taking encourages employees to engage in exploratory knowledge-related activities. This visionary aspect of KOL fosters a long-term orientation (knowledge exploration activities take time and may not always be successful), as well as flexibility in setting new directions in response to changing knowledge contexts. On the other hand, KOL's transactional behaviour aims to improve work processes by leveraging existing knowledge frameworks. The proclivity for marginal improvement enhances efficiency, stability, and control in the use of knowledge. This managerial leadership style clarifies work responsibilities, explains performance expectations, and sets standard routines and procedures to maintain consistent performance, ultimately leading to goal attainment. Employees' ability to deliver results in line with the expected goals determines the exchange or promise of rewards and benefits. A transactional system ensures that employees use their knowledge to coordinate their efforts in accordance with specified standards and goals. This reduces the experience of deviations from set goals, which carry their own risks and costs. The path goal theory suggests that a leader's effectiveness in achieving desired work attitudes is contingent on his or her ability to adapt appropriate leadership styles in varied situations.

KOL balances the tensions that arise from both leadership qualities to ensure the effective integration of knowledge resources for creative work. However, it is important to mention that the set of leadership behaviours required to achieve a state of balance often evolves as employees progress on a given knowledge-related task or assignment. In other words, leaders should be able to adjust either simultaneously or sequentially between transformational and transactional behaviours in changing work processes.

This ensures that the strengths and benefits of both leadership styles are realised at different points in time and situations (Akıncı et al., 2022; Alghamdi, 2018). Focusing on knowledge exploitation alone could lead to stagnation or redundancy of efforts, leaving organisations vulnerable to the changing influences of exogenous factors. Conversely, an overly concentrated focus on knowledge exploration without a corresponding pursuit of operational discipline and excellence (via knowledge exploitation) can cause an organisation to lose advantages it once had to others who are better equipped to execute. Hence, there is a need for a paradoxical mindset on the part of leaders.

2.2 Creative Work Engagement

Creative work engagement (also known as creative process engagement or creative work involvement) is the extent to which employees commit their attention, cognition, and energy to problem identification, information search and gathering, idea generation, idea evaluation, and idea pitch (Nnadozie et al., 2019). An idea pitch, which is a culmination of efforts made during the creative process, transmits a novel and useful idea. According to Atwater and Carmeli (2009), to achieve creative outcomes like creative self-efficacy, employee creativity, and employee innovation, organisations must motivate employees to actively participate in creative work processes. The novelty of these outcomes enables organisations and employees to maintain knowledge-based advantages to advance in changing environments. Furthermore, creative work engagement predicts other individual, team, and organisational outcomes. For example, employee performance, intention to stay, organisational commitment, job satisfaction, and organisational citizenship behaviour are outcomes of creative task engagement (Saks, 2006). The social exchange process, which provides both tangible and intangible support for creative actions, influences employees with creative potential to either participate in creative activities or not. As a result, job resources help satisfy employees' productive needs for achieving their creativity and innovation goals.

2.3 Knowledge Sharing

According to Ononye (2023:954), "knowledge sharing is the extent to which employees share contextual and actionable information and know-how with others to enable the initiation, execution, and completion of specific tasks and assignments." In order to obtain value, employees often exchange knowledge in both tacit and explicit forms. Tacit knowledge is personal and subjective knowledge that reflects practical experiences and thoughts as one interacts with his or her environment. Conversely, explicit knowledge involves articulating it in formal languages and disseminating it through print or electronic documents. While both types of knowledge are essential for fostering creativity, the leadership task involves elucidating the specifics of personal knowledge, which often remains hidden and constitutes the bulk of organisational knowledge. As a result, the focus is on externalising relevant and valuable aspects of tacit knowledge for others to access and use. Socialisation practices, such as face-to-face interactions, meetings, communities of practice, and brainstorming sessions, often facilitate the successful sharing of tacit knowledge. Knowledge sharing, however, can be the source

of employees' creative actions in managing evolving work and organisational challenges. Knowledge remains passive and lacks value until it is shared and integrated into individual and organisational memory. In fact, knowledge sharing triggers other knowledge-related practices, like knowledge creation, knowledge integration, and learning, because employees use what they know to facilitate different activities (Ononye, 2021). Therefore, it holds significance in an organisation's knowledge management framework, as it establishes a connection between the location of knowledge and its productive application to maximise value (Ononye & Igwe, 2019).

2.4 Knowledge-oriented Leadership and Creative Work Engagement

Generally, research examining the KOL's influence on employee creative engagement is scant, yet it has emphasised the significance of the KOL on creative work engagement outcomes, such as employee creativity, creative performance, and innovation. For instance, research (Naqshbandi & Jasumuddin, 2018; Zia, 2020; Rehman & Iqbal, 2020) has observed that KOL plays a critical role in fostering innovation, which stems from employees' creative efforts both individually and collectively. According to Men and Jia (2024), KOL influences team members' creativity through learning. By allowing the exchange of valuable information for problem solving, team members can apply and learn from the insights and experiences of others to enhance creative thinking. KOL builds trusting relationships to create a safe space for knowledge sharing with leadership and employees, which in turn improves employee creativity (Ononye & Madumezia, 2024). Knowledge sharing is an expression of trust among individuals in a supportive social exchange process. Although KOL influences employee creativity, involvement in the creative process is the first step towards realising it (Zhang & Bartol, 2010; Chen et al., 2022). In other words, employees' productive engagements in creative work processes set the foundations for creative achievements.

Research also considered KOL's influence on attitudinal constructs, particularly work engagement. Shamin et al. (2017) suggest that this leadership style influences work attitudes, such as creative self-efficacy and work engagement, leading to the demonstration of knowledge management behaviour. It is important for employees to have the right attitude to facilitate behaviours focused on sharing, creating, and applying knowledge. This creates a supportive organisational climate for creativity and innovation. A recent study (Chughtai & Khan, 2024) confirmed KOL's role in improving work engagement for better employee innovation performance. Although work engagement focuses on employees' general attitude towards work, creative work engagement, as a subset, limits itself to employees' attitude towards participation in creative work. Some studies focused on KOL aspects and found a positive association between them and employee creative engagement. On one hand, Saeed et al. (2019) documented the positive influence of transformational leadership on employee creative engagement. On the other hand, focusing on the effect of transactional leadership in Vietnam's public sector, Nguyen and Nguyen (2022) suggested that this leadership style

positively influences employees' creative engagements at work. They also mentioned that because employees have no intention to leave, they will comply with tasks regardless of the leadership styles in use. Nonetheless, when they use rewards to motivate employees to meet work expectations, their influence is more significant. For purposeful attitudinal change in the public sector, linking work goals to rewards is important (Thanh et al., 2022). The ambidexterity argument suggests that balancing tension between opposing leadership styles enhances creative behaviours by meeting employees' needs to engage in either or both exploration and exploitation activities. Given the above, we can infer a relationship between KOL and creative process engagement. Therefore, we hypothesise that:

H1: The influence of knowledge-oriented leadership on creative work engagement is positive and significant.

2.5 The Mediating Role of Knowledge Sharing

Research demonstrates that leadership facilitates knowledge sharing, which influences employees' creative engagement and learning in their work roles (Ononye, 2023). For instance, Chen et al. (2022) proposed that knowledge sharing indirectly explains the influence of servant leadership on creative work engagement. Joo et al. (2023) found that empowering leaders had an insignificant influence on employee creativity except through knowledge sharing. Saeed et al. (2019) noted that leader-member exchange, marked by the exchange of supportive resources, enhances employee creative process engagement; thus, the sharing of domain knowledge could provide context in the relationship dynamics between managers and employees. Arguably, positive forms of leadership, characterised by the stimulation of positive employee emotions and outlook, influence knowledge sharing and ultimately drive creative work engagement. KOL, as a positive leadership style, can foster this sequence of effects on employees.

Other studies have examined the mediational value of knowledge sharing in the nexus between leadership aspects associated with KOL and employee creativity. For example, Hussain et al. (2017) revealed that transactional leadership and knowledge sharing influence creativity, and knowledge can provide an effective mediating context between this leadership style and creativity. They concluded that the transactional leadership style could provide better employee motivation to share knowledge by giving them suitable rewards and clear direction for attaining goals. Tran et al. (2021) studied the mediating factors impacting the transformational leadership and employee creativity nexus and found creative self-efficacy, innovation climate, and knowledge sharing to have a significant and positive mediational value. Nguyen et al. (2024) affirmed that knowledge sharing could mediate both transformational and transactional leadership influence on employee creativity under the moderating conditions of an organisational innovation climate. Devi (2024), who studied the relationship between paradoxical leadership (i.e., the use of two opposing leadership styles) and employee creativity, mentioned that knowledge sharing rather than knowledge hiding mediated the

relationship. Arguably, the paradox of transformational and transactional leadership, as exemplified in KOL, fosters knowledge sharing, not knowledge hiding, in order to promote employee creativity.

In addition, research demonstrates that knowledge sharing mediates KOL's relationship with other valued outcomes of employee creative engagement. For instance, Zia (2020) and Chughtai and Khan (2024) found that knowledge sharing practices serve as a mediatory pathway through which KOL affects innovation at the individual and organisational level. KOL facilitates knowledge sharing by nurturing one's confidence in his/her ability to share knowledge, fostering enjoyment in helping others with their knowledge, and encouraging willingness to share important work-related knowledge with others (Mustika et al., 2022). All these helps to accelerate creative thinking and action among employees in the workplace. Prior studies have consistently demonstrated a positive mediating effect of knowledge sharing on KOL and other valued outcomes, particularly innovation. However, we argue that this effect may also extend to creative process engagement, given the concept's direct and indirect links to innovation-related concepts. This led to the formulation of three hypotheses:

H₂: The influence of knowledge sharing on creative work engagement is positive and significant.

H₃: The influence of knowledge-oriented leadership on knowledge sharing is positive and significant

H₄: Knowledge sharing mediates the positive and significant influence of knowledge-oriented leadership on creative work engagement.

3. Theoretical Framework

3.1 Social Exchange Theory

The social exchange theory could explain employees' attitudes and behaviours in exchange processes in a social setting. The theory states that employees' evaluations of the potential benefits and costs of engaging in a specific relationship with a leader determine their work attitude and behaviour. Their attitudes and behaviours reflect the decisions they make about their participation in the exchange process. Arguably, a leader who supports employees' use of personal, organisational, and external knowledge for organisational work will reinforce a positive work attitude in reciprocation. The exchange of knowledge activates attitudinal processes, which may sometimes be discretionary but highly valuable to the execution and completion of tasks and assignments. Employees can creatively respond to changing work demands and requirements by productively leveraging shared knowledge. Employees typically perform better in a supportive exchange process than in a less supportive one (Ononye, 2023), and they also tend to model behaviours valued by supportive leaders to sustain the transmission of rewards and benefits. A high-quality exchange process will engender valued outcomes for both the leader and the employee. However, it is important to note

that diminishing marginal utility may occur as a particular reward or benefit for an action becomes less valuable when given repeatedly (Cook & Rice, 2006). As a result, there is a need for a transactional exchange system to improve coordination and control for consistent efforts. While KOL's transformational qualities ensure motivation for using shared knowledge to drive organisational activities, their transactional qualities tie rewards and incentives to work roles and performance expectations. This improves the coordination of employees' efforts to achieve the desired goals. The combination of these qualities reinforces positive attitudes, and creative work involvement is one of them.

Figure 1: The research model
Source: Developed by the researchers, 2024

4. Methodology

The study surveyed the clinical staff in a government-owned hospital in Asaba, Delta State. A proximate organisation and geography could significantly reduce the time and resources expended in conducting a more nuanced observation and examination of the concepts. According to Yamane's sample size determination formula, the study's population was 381 (Records and Statistics, 2023), with a sample size of 195. Given the stressful nature of their jobs, the study employed convenience sampling. A structured questionnaire was developed from the validated and standardised scales of previous studies as the data collection tool. Please see the next paragraph for questionnaire development, which identifies these studies. A covering letter was attached to the questionnaire indicating the research aim, an anonymity statement, and a request to complete the survey instrument. The questionnaire was personally administered to the target respondents, who consented and voluntarily participated in the survey. The survey was conducted in the month of February 2024. Eventually, the usable questionnaires collected were 191, indicating a 97.9 percent response rate. The demographic characteristics of the respondents revealed that 77 were males and 114 were females, with a mean age of 44.9 years. The respondents were mostly permanent employees (167, 88.4%), and their mean tenure was 15.4 years. All the respondents have tertiary education. The respondents' professional backgrounds showed that they were doctors (71), nurses (78), pharmacists (2), and allied health professionals (40).

Donate & Sánchez de Pablo (2014) provided the six measurement items for KOL. Prior studies (e.g., Naqshbandi & Jasumuddin, 2018; Zia, 2020) have used this scale to demonstrate the effect of KOL on other organisational variables. The sample item reads, “Managers promote learning from experience, tolerating mistakes up to a certain point.” The three knowledge-sharing questions were adapted from Ononye (2021). One of the sample items is “I share suggestions, ideas, and solutions with people in my department and/or organisation.” Zhang and Bartol (2010) provided the eleven question items for the creative work engagement scale. This scale measures the level of employees’ participation in problem identification, information searching and encoding, and idea generation to pitch a creative idea or demonstrate creativity in the workplace. A sample item includes “I think about a problem from multiple perspectives.” The scales’ response options ranged from very frequently (5) to not at all (1). See appendix 1 for the complete measurement items.

Although we used validated scales from previous studies to ensure content validity, we subjected the questionnaire to a reliability test for internal consistency prior to administering it to the target respondents. This was performed on 15 respondents, conveniently selected from the study’s population. The Cronbach alphas for the latent constructs were 0.745, 0.881, and 0.802 for KOL, knowledge sharing, and creative work engagement, respectively. The scales were deemed reliable because their scores exceeded the minimum limit of 0.70.

The study used structural equation modelling (SEM) based on the partial least squares (PLS) approach for data analysis and hypothesis testing. This test was aided by the SmartPLS 4 analytical software. This SEM technique can achieve stable estimation for a relatively small sample size and does not have strict conditions on the residual distribution of data. This explains the growing popularity and use of this technique among management scholars. The study employed the two-step approach of Anderson and Gerbing (1998), which estimated the measurement model (or outer model) for reliability and validity and, subsequently, the structural model (or inner model) for hypothesis testing.

5. Results and Discussion

5.1 Results

For the analysis, the study used 191 questionnaires, and this number is above the acceptable sample size of 100 needed to achieve stable estimations based on the PLS approach to SEM (Hair & Alamer, 2022). Before performing the PLS analysis, the data normality was checked to ensure that the items had normal distributional properties, even though the lack of normality is not a major concern when using PLS. Non-normally distributed data may cause inflated and biased model parameters and estimations (Hair & Alamer, 2022). The study observed from the PLS output sheet that the skewness values of the measurement items ranged from -1.784 to 1.681, which were

within the acceptable range of -2 to +2, as recommended by Hair et al. (2022). Given this, the study advanced to the two-step SEM approach. The first step is to test the measurement model for the validity and reliability of the latent constructs. Five quality criteria were used for this purpose: standardised factor loadings, average variance extracted (AVE), composite reliability, variance inflation factor, and the Fornell-Larcker criterion. They measure item reliability, convergent validity, construct reliability, multicollinearity issues, and discriminant validity, respectively. Hair et al. (2022) provided the rule of thumb for result interpretation. However, the constructs' overall mean scores were high, suggesting their clear expression in public hospital activities.

Table 1
Measurement Model Results

	Latent Constructs	Mean	FL Range > 0.707	CR > 0.70	AVE > 0.50	VIF	Discriminant Validity		
							1	2	3
1	KOL	3.878	0.826 – 0.8	0.782	0.719	1.629	0.789		
2	KS	4.135	0.830 – 0.8	0.817	0.733	2.015	0.264	0.796	
3	CWE	3.924	0.778 – 0.8	0.794	0.695		0.307	0.344	0.777

Source: Authors' PLS Computational Output of Field Survey

Note: KOL = knowledge-oriented leadership, KS = knowledge sharing, CWE = Creative work engagement, FL = factor loading, CR = Composite reliability, AVE = Average variance extracted, VIF = Variance inflation factor.

Table 1 shows the measurement model estimate for KOL, knowledge sharing, and creative work engagement. The FL range revealed that the measurement items for each construct had coefficients above the recommended cut-off point of 0.707, indicating a relationship between the measurement items and their underlying latent construct. This establishes satisfactory item reliability. The study used the CR values to ascertain the reliability of each construct, and they were above the acceptable value of 0.70, suggesting that each latent construct achieved acceptable construct reliability. Furthermore, the measurement model demonstrated adequate convergent validity among the constructs using the AVE values, which were higher than the minimum value of 0.50. The variance inflation factor (VIF) values, which measure the extent of multicollinearity among predictors, were below the acceptable limit of 5.0. Thus, the predictors were not perfectly correlated, and inferences made from the measurement model estimations were valid and reliable.

The study also used the VIF to check for common method bias problems in the data, and found values below the recommended cut-off point of 3.0 (Kock, 2015), indicating no issues with the measurement items or the dataset. The Fornell-Larcker criterion showed that the coefficients of each latent construct were greater than their inter-construct coefficients. Therefore, the study observed discriminant validity among the latent constructs. Overall, the measurement model was of excellent quality, given that the criteria exceeded the recommended acceptance threshold. After achieving this, the

study performed the second step, which involves estimating the structural model for hypothesis testing.

Table 2
Structural Model Results

Hypothesised Relationship		Model 1 β ($p < 0.05$)	Model 2 β ($p < 0.05$)	Decision
H1	Knowledge-oriented leadership → Creative work engagement	0.234 (0.000)	0.229 (0.000)	Accept
H2	Knowledge sharing → Creative work engagement	0.439 (0.000)	0.440 (0.000)	Accept
H3	Knowledge-oriented leadership → Knowledge sharing		0.257 (0.000)	Accept
H4	Knowledge-oriented leadership → Knowledge sharing → Creative work engagement		0.101 (0.000)	Accept
R ²		0.380	0.397	
SRMR		0.078	0.075	
NFI		0.82	0.84	

Source: Authors' PLS Computational Output of Field Survey.

The structural model was examined with beta coefficients (β) and p-values to determine the nature of the relationship and its significance to the hypothesised model. The study used the R², standardised root mean squared residual (SRMR), and normed fit index (NFI) to check the predictive quality of the structural model. The bootstrapping method using 10000 subsamples was also used to evaluate the significance of the hypothesised relationship. Furthermore, the study applied Baron and Kenny's (1986) mediation approach to assess the contextual importance of knowledge sharing.

Hypotheses 1 and 2 propose that KOL and knowledge sharing have positive and significant influences on creative work engagement. The PLS result showed that the propositions were true, as it was both positive and significant for KOL and creative work engagement ($\beta = 0.234$, $p = 0.000$) and knowledge sharing and creative work engagement ($\beta = 0.439$, $p = 0.000$). Therefore, the study rejected the null hypotheses, which suggests a statistically insignificant direct influence, and accepted the alternate hypotheses 1 and 2.

Hypothesis 3 states that the influence of KOL on knowledge sharing is positive and significant. The PLS result provides ample evidence to validate this statement ($\beta = 0.257$, $p = 0.000$). Therefore, we rejected the null hypothesis that KOL does not have a positive and significant influence on knowledge sharing and accepted the alternate hypothesis. Hypothesis 4 posits that knowledge sharing mediates the positive and significant influence of KOL on creative work involvement. The specific-indirect PLS result confirmed the validity of this argument ($\beta = 0.101$, $p = 0.000$). Thus, the significant result, which confirms the strong mediational value of knowledge sharing, means we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternate hypothesis.

Model 2 added a link from KOL to knowledge sharing. This reduced KOL's influence on creative work engagement by 0.005 points. However, the effect was still positive and significant. Thus, the mediation type is partial and complementary in nature. Furthermore, model 1, which showed the direct effects of the independent and mediating constructs on the dependent construct, accounted for 38 percent of the variance in creative work engagement. In model 2, the creation of the mediating pathway improved this percentage by 1.7 percent. Following Cohen's (1998) R^2 categorisation, R^2 scores above 26 percent indicate a large or significant effect in the variance of the outcome or dependent variable. According to Hair et al. (2022), a good fit was established using only SRMR, as the SRMR values were below the cut-off point of 0.80 and the NFI values were not above the recommended cut-off of 0.90.

5.2. Discussion

The study found that KOL positively and significantly influences creative work engagement, suggesting that KOL drives employee involvement in creative processes by balancing their needs to participate in exploitative and explorative knowledge-related activities. Although studies have yet to investigate the influence of KOL on creative work engagement, they have examined its outcomes, particularly creativity and innovation (e.g., Naqshbandi & Jasumuddin, 2018; Zia, 2020; Rehman & Iqbal, 2020; Men & Jia, 2024; and Ononye & Madumezia, 2024). KOL is relevant in triggering purposeful attitudinal change in contexts strongly associated with sharing, creating, and applying knowledge, as is the case with creative and innovative processes. In fact, the reinforcement of certain work attitudes, such as creative work engagement, serves as a catalyst for the activation of knowledge-related processes critical to unlocking aspects of knowledge marked by novelty and discovery (Shamin et al., 2017). Nevertheless, this study extends the list of KOL's outcomes by unravelling its effect on creative work engagement.

The study found that KOL positively and significantly influences knowledge sharing, suggesting that this leadership style facilitates the exchange of important work-related information for understanding and creatively solving problems. This confirms the position of previous studies (Zia, 2020; Chughtai & Khan, 2024), which reported enhanced knowledge management activities, including knowledge sharing, as one of the benefits of KOL. The study also revealed that knowledge sharing positively and significantly influences creative work engagement, suggesting that employees must engage in the sharing of valuable knowledge to foster productive participation in creative activities. Indeed, the relevance of knowledge sharing for creativity-related concepts lies in its ability to guide employees from where knowledge resides to its optimal utilisation for value creation. This finding is consistent with researchers (Saeed et al., 2019; Chen et al., 2022; Joo et al., 2023) who reported a positive association between knowledge sharing and creative work engagement.

The study found that knowledge sharing mediates the positive and significant influence of KOL on creative work engagement. While existing studies have yet to establish the

mediational importance of knowledge sharing in the KOL and creative work engagement nexus, this study supports the notion that positive leadership styles influence knowledge sharing, which in turn influences creative work engagement. Previous studies (Saeed et al., 2019; Chen et al., 2022; Joo et al., 2023) examined the mediation of knowledge sharing by other positive leadership styles on creative work engagement, which led to this argument. Also, the results are similar to those of other studies (Hussain et al., 2017; Tran et al., 2021; Devi, 2024; Nguyen et al., 2024) that found the same positive sequence when transactional and/or transformational leadership qualities were present. The paradox of transformational and transactional leadership, as exemplified in KOL, encourages knowledge sharing to get employees more involved in creative work processes. Regarding studies on KOL's influences, the study found agreement on the positive mediating effect of knowledge sharing on discretionary work attitudes and behaviours and extended the possible outcomes that KOL can achieve through knowledge sharing. Studies (Donate & Sánchez de Pablo, 2014; Rehman & Iqbal, 2020; Zia, 2020; Chughtai & Khan, 2024) reported that KOL influences innovation, a discretionary behavioural activity, through knowledge sharing. Although knowledge sharing has a partial and complementary effect, KOL influence was more significant indirectly than directly. This may explain the rationale for developing and maintaining responsive knowledge management practices to make the best use of shared knowledge resources at the right time, place, and context. In all, the argument grounded in the social exchange theory was confirmed, which states that KOL supports the best use of knowledge by strengthening the knowledge sharing activities of employees and, in turn, allows them to voluntarily engage in creative processes associated with work. The supportive relationship formed by KOL allows employees to feel obligated to reciprocate by sharing knowledge critical to effective participation in creative activities in the organisation.

6. Conclusion

The study presented an integrated framework including direct and indirect paths linking knowledge-oriented leadership to creative work engagement. Data were obtained from a sample of 191 conveniently drawn from a public hospital in Asaba, Delta State, and analysed using the partial least squares (PLS) analytical technique. The PLS analysis showed that knowledge-oriented leadership's influence on creative work engagement can be elucidated both directly and indirectly through knowledge sharing, a complementary knowledge-related activity. The study concludes that knowledge-oriented leaders can achieve an optimal influence on creative work engagement by fostering the sharing of knowledge among employees. Consequently, the study recommends the following:

1. Leadership trainings should be curated to develop ambidextrous behaviours associated with knowledge-oriented leadership with a focus on enhanced communication and motivation. Organisations should frequently develop in-house leadership trainings and sponsor employees, partly or fully, to externally organised programmes and trainings. Furthermore, organisations, particularly

public hospitals, should appoint, recruit, and/or recognise individuals who demonstrate leadership behaviours that seek to make the best use of knowledge via its exploitation and exploration. The selection of such a leader will facilitate knowledge sharing, allowing shared knowledge to reach its full potential when put to use in the workplace.

2. Organisations should rightly cultivate and maintain the knowledge sharing culture, given its centrality in the knowledge-oriented leadership and creative work engagement nexus. The unlocking of interactive and collaborative activities, such as brainstorming sessions, meetings, communities of practice, face-to-face interactions, and in-house seminars, allows for enhanced knowledge sharing, which accelerates or promotes employees' engagement in creative tasks and assignments. Adopting an open-door policy or suggestion boxes can go a long way toward triggering the exchange of context-relevant knowledge with management.
3. The leadership should leverage knowledge management activities, such as knowledge sharing, to maximise their influence on employees' attitudes towards workplace creativity. Employees should receive clear communication about the importance of knowledge sharing and management's expectations for employees' participation in the sharing of knowledge. This is critical for making passive and hidden knowledge more active and productive in the workplace. Promoting knowledge sharing is crucial for learning in a rapidly changing work environment.

Acknowledgement: The researchers want to appreciate the reviewers for their constructive observations to improve the quality of this paper.

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APPENDIX 1
MEASUREMENT ITEMS

Knowledge-oriented Leadership (KoL)

1. Leadership has been creating an environment for responsible employee behavior and teamwork
2. Managers are used to assuming the role of knowledge leaders, which is mainly characterized by openness, tolerance of mistakes, and mediation for the achievement of the firm's objectives.
3. Managers promote learning from experience, tolerating mistakes up to a certain point (K-OL3).
4. Managers behave as advisers, and controls are just an assessment of the accomplishment of objectives (K-OL4). Transactional
5. Managers promote the acquisition of external knowledge (K-OL5).
6. Managers reward employees who share and apply their knowledge (K-OL6). Transactional

Knowledge Sharing (KS)

7. I share suggestions, ideas, and solutions with people in my department and/or organisation.
8. I consult others in my department and/or organisation so that they can share their suggestions, ideas, and solutions with me.
9. I interact with people in my organisation to create a shared or common understanding of a problem and how to handle it.

Creative Work Engagement (CWE)

10. I spend considerable time trying to understand the nature of the problem.
11. I think about the problem from multiple perspectives.
12. I decompose a difficult problem/assignment into parts to obtain greater understanding.
13. I consult a wide variety of information.
14. I search for information from multiple sources (e.g., personal memories, others' experience, documentation, Internet, etc.).
15. I retain large amounts of detailed information in my area of expertise for future use.
16. I consider diverse sources of information in generating new ideas.
17. I look for connections with solutions used in seeming diverse areas.
18. I generate a significant number of alternatives to the same problem before I choose the final solution.
19. I try to devise potential solutions that move away from established ways of doing things.
20. I spend considerable time shifting through information that helps to generate new ideas.